

Brian's List of Genealogy/History Journal, Newsletter Articles, & Blogs, as well as Diary/Selected Essays/Poems, Personal Writings, etc.

by Brian Paul Kaess

October 29, 2025

1. See article 'The Dorschke's of Silesia- Ethnic Poles Who Fought for the Germans' by Brian Paul Kaess, in Fall 2016 issue of the Rodziny, journal of the Polish Genealogical Society of America (PGSA).
2. See article 'Facebook Helps Find Branch of Dorschke Family,' by Brian Paul Kaess, Nov/Dec 2018 issue of Das Posthorn, newsletter for the SW Florida Germanic Genealogy Society (SWFLGGS)
3. See article 'Lonely Letter Helps Find Kaess Heimat' by Brian Paul Kaess, Jan/Feb 2019 issue of Das Posthorn, newsletter for the SW Florida Germanic Genealogy Society (SWFLGGS).
4. See article 'Connecting the Swartz' of Virginia to the Kauffman's of Switzerland,' by Brian Paul Kaess, Mar/April 2019 issue of Das Posthorn, newsletter for the SW Florida Germanic Genealogy Society (SWFLGGS).
5. See article 'A Vacation to Remember for a Lifetime' by Brian Paul Kaess in May/June 2019 issue of Das Posthorn, newsletter for the SW Florida Germanic Genealogy Society (SWFLGGS).
6. See also, 'Coming Across a Denazification File for Paul Ernst Kaess in the Staatsarchiv Ludwigsburg,' by Brian Paul Kaess in Sept 2019 issue of Das Posthorn, newsletter for the SW Florida Germanic Genealogy Society (SWFLGGS).
7. See article by Brian Paul Kaess 'Lonely Letter Helps Find Kaess Family' in Spring/Summer 2018 issue of Germanic Genealogy Journal, journal of the Germanic Genealogy Society (GGS). This issue was delayed for publication until April 2019.
8. See article by Brian Paul Kaess, 'Distant Cousin helps fill out Family Tree of Kokot Family in Silesia,' on p. 49 in Spring/Summer 2022 issue of Germanic Genealogy Journal, journal of the Germanic Genealogy Society (GGS).
9. See article by Brian Paul Kaess, 'Was Gerd Kaess Lutheran or Catholic?' on p. 27 in the Fall/Winter 2023 issue of the Germanic Genealogy Journal, journal of the Germanic Genealogy Society (GGS).
10. See article 'My Experiences at the Edge: Working at the Edgewater Medical Center in the 1980's and 1990's' by Brian Paul Kaess on pp. 4-5 of the Winter 2020 edition of the Edgewater Scrapbook, newsletter for the Edgewater Historical Society (EHS). Here is a link to the Edgewater Scrapbook archive: [v31-4 2020 Winter | Edgewater Historical Society \(edgewaterhistory.org\)](https://www.edgewaterhistory.org/v31-4-2020-winter)
11. See 'Letter to the Editor' by Brian Paul Kaess in Der Kurier newsletter of December 2017, Volume 35, No. 4, p. 109. Der Kurier is a newsletter of the Mid-Atlantic Germanic Society (MAGS). Brian Paul Kaess' name also appears at the bottom of the same page as a new member.
12. See post 'My Family Connection to Robert E Lee' by Brian Paul Kaess at Civil War Talk, published February 9, 2024, as [My Family Connection to Robert E Lee | Researching Civil War Records & Ancestry \(civilwartalk.com\)](https://www.civilwartalk.com/my-family-connection-to-robert-e-lee)
13. See post 'Pvt. Joseph Godfrey Swartz, Virginia Reserves Infantry' by Brian Paul Kaess in Civil War Talk, published April 7, 2024, as [Pvt. Joseph Godfrey Swartz, Virginia Reserves Infantry | Biographic Profiles - We Will Remember \(civilwartalk.com\)](https://www.civilwartalk.com/pvt-joseph-godfrey-swartz-virginia-reserves-infantry-biographic-profiles-we-will-remember)
14. See 'My Silesian Family Ancestry' by Brian Paul Kaess at Blogspot.com, published August 18, 2025, at [My Silesian Family Ancestry](https://www.blogger.com/blog-post/My-Silesian-Family-Ancestry)
15. See 'Ancestors of Robert E Gibboney' Forum Post at 'Reaching Out Ireland' at [Ancestors of Robert E Gibboney | Ireland Reaching Out \(irelandxo.com\)](https://www.irelandxo.com) published April 7 2024 by Brian Paul Kaess
16. See Pvt. John Jacob Haller/Heller biography entry for SAR database, written by descendant Brian Paul Kaess: [Patriot Research System – National Society Sons of the American Revolution \(sar.org\)](https://www.sar.org)

17. See 'A Tale from My Tree: My Silesian Family Ancestry' by Brian Paul Kaess on p. 72 in the Summer 2024 issue of the Polish Eaglet, journal of the Polish Genealogical Society of Michigan (PGSM).
18. Brian Paul Kaess is also mentioned as a new member and such in the Dixon Blue Light News, newsletter for the Sons of Confederate Veterans (SCV) Lt. George E. Dixon Camp #1962 in Belleville, IL, sometime in 2011. He is erroneously mentioned as a Graduate of Northwestern University. The Editor Gale Red made this mistake. There is also a Death Notice for his mom Marie Ellen Dawson Kaess (1945-2012) in the same newsletter on p. 3 in November 2012.
19. See 'Pvt. Joseph Godfrey Swartz (1847-1887): Scholar of the Valley, Son of a Vanished Cause' by Brian Paul Kaess on October 19, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Single page. See Link: Pvt. Joseph Godfrey Swartz (1847–1887): Scholar of the Valley, Son of a Vanished Cause
20. See 'Robert E. Gibboney: A Life Etched in Stone and Storm,' by Brian Paul Kaess on October 28, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Two pp. See Link: Robert E. Gibboney: A Life Etched in Stone and Storm
21. See article by Brian Paul Kaess, 'Three Villages from Bessarabia, Russia' on pp. 25-27 in the Fall 2024 Issue of the Journal of the American Historical Society of the Germans from Russia, journal of the American Historical Society of Germans from Russia (AHSGR).
22. See 'Brian Paul Kaess Diary From 2022 to 2024' by Brian Paul Kaess on July 22, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Twelve pp. See Link: Brian Paul Kaess Diary: 2022 to 2024 Brian wrote this Diary while living in Mexico. Also available at Allen County Public Library Genealogy Center in Ft. Wayne, Indiana in their Family Resources section under Kaess Family Materials. See Link: Kaess Family Materials - ACPL Genealogy Center There was also a copy submitted to the Library of Congress.
23. See 'Pfc. Talmage Edward Dawson, U.S. Army in France during WWI' on pp. 8-11 by Brian Paul Kaess in November 2024 issue of Kansas Review (Journal News), newsletter for the Kansas Council of Genealogical Societies (KCGS).
24. See 'Letter to the Editor' by Brian Kaess on October 12, 1989, edition of San Antonio Express
25. See post 'Looking for Jewish Marriage Records for Sarata, Bessarabia, Russia' by Brian Paul Kaess on August 9, 2024, in Jewish Gen at main@groups.jewishgen.org | Looking for Jewish Marriage Records for Sarata, Bessarabia, Russia
26. See 'Gerd Edwin Paul Kaess Biography' by Brian Paul Kaess on October 17, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Two pp. See Link: Gerd Edwin Paul Kaess Biography
27. See 'Marie Ellen Dawson Biography' by Brian Paul Kaess on October 19, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Two pp. See Link: Marie Ellen Dawson Biography
28. See mention of 'Talmage Edward Dawson, WWI Dough Boy from Topeka, Kansas' by Brian Paul Kaess in December 2024 issue of News & Views, enewsletter of the Topeka Genealogical Society. Also see link: Talmage Dawson story with images edited
29. See 'David Bennett Dawson (1857-1902): A Life Forged in Steam and Steel' by Brian Paul Kaess at Zenodo.org on October 18, 2025. Single page. See Link: David Bennett Dawson (1857–1902): A Life Forged in Steam and Steel
30. See 'Alvira "Allie" Elizabeth Mansfield (1864-1932): A Life of Grace beneath the Rails and Skyline' by Brian Paul Kaess on October 18, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Two pp. See Link: Alvira "Allie" Elizabeth Mansfield (1864–1932): A Life of Grace Beneath the Rails and Skyline
31. See 'Letter to the Editor' by Brian Paul Kaess in December 5, 2024, edition of the Northern Star, student newspaper of Northern Illinois University. See Link: Express Yourself: Don't forget about Ukraine! – Northern Star
32. See 'Some Tidbits or Loose Ends about the Military' by Brian Paul Kaess on September 19, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Three pp. See Link: Some Tidbits or Loose Ends about the Military
33. See 'You Shall Be Purified! A Cataloging of Greater & Lesser Mysteries in Ancient Greece & Rome' by Brian Paul Kaess on October 7, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Four pp. See Link: "You Shall Be Purified! A Cataloging of Greater & Lesser Mysteries in Ancient Greece & Rome"
34. See 'Reimagining Schliemann's Troy' by Brian Paul Kaess on June 21, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Seven pp. See Link: Reimagining Schliemann's Troy
35. See 'Why Alexander the Great should have accepted Darius III's offer of half the Persian Kingdom,' by Brian Paul Kaess on July 1, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Six pp. See Link: Why Alexander

- the Great should have accepted Darius III's offer of half the Persian Kingdom
36. See 'Some Problems or Paradoxes in Letters relating to Columbus' Four Voyages to the New World' by Brian Paul Kaess on September 20, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Six pp.; See Link: Some Problems or Paradoxes in Letters relating to Columbus' Four Voyages to the New World
 37. See 'Brian Paul Kaess & Ellen Byrd Elliott take a Family Vacation' by Brian Paul Kaess on June 27, 2025. Three pp.; See Link: Brian Paul Kaess & Ellen Byrd Elliott take a Family Vacation
 38. See 'Cruising Chicago's Club Scene with the Yakster' by Brian Paul Kaess on June 27, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Three pp.; See Link: Cruising Chicago's Club Scene with the Yakster
 39. See 'Brian Paul Kaess' Time as a Registrar at Gordon Tech High School' by Brian Paul Kaess on September 20, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Three Pages. See Link: Brian Paul Kaess' Time as a Registrar at Gordon Tech High School
 40. See 'Norman Allen Langley Biography & tidbits' by Brian Paul Kaess on September 23, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Two pp. See Link: Norman Allen Langley Biography & tidbits
 41. See 'Margaret Jane Swartz Biography & tidbits' by Brian Paul Kaess on October 17, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Three pp. See Link: Margaret Jane Swartz Biography & tidbits
 42. See 'Garret Thomas Kaess: From Poverty to Prestige- A Life of Grit, Genius and Global Reach' by Brian Paul Kaess on October 27, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Three pp. See Link: Garret Thomas Kaess: From Poverty to Prestige—A Life of Grit, Genius, and Global Reach
 43. See 'Brian Paul Kaess Autobiography' by Brian Paul Kaess on October 26, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Eleven pp. See Link: Brian Paul Kaess Autobiography
 44. See 'Brian Paul Kaess Family Documentation' by Brian Paul Kaess on October 24, 2025, at Zenodo.org. A collection of images/documents/pdf's/articles. See Link: Brian Paul Kaess Family Documentation
 45. See 'Delomelanicon (shorter English version)' by Brian Paul Kaess on October 14, 2025, at Internet Archive. 39 pp. See Link: Delomelanicon (shorter English version) : Brian Paul Kaess : Free Download, Borrow, and Streaming : Internet Archive
 46. See 'LCpl. Brian Paul Kaess in the U.S. Marines in Cuba' by Brian Paul Kaess on June 22, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Six pp. See Link: LCpl. Brian Paul Kaess in the U.S. Marines in Cuba
 47. See 'Pfc. Brian Paul Kaess in the U.S. Army at Fort Belvoir, Virginia during the Cold War' by Brian Paul Kaess on September 20, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Seven pp. See Link: Pfc. Brian Paul Kaess in the U.S. Army at Fort Belvoir, Virginia during the Cold War
 48. See "God's Will": My Family Connection to Confederate General Robert E. Lee by Brian Paul Kaess on August 26, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Nine pp. See Link: "God's Will": My Family Connection to Confederate General Robert E. Lee
 49. See "Mit schwarz Grunde und Tapfer Keit": The Military Record of Sgt. Paul Ernst Kaess by Brian Paul Kaess on October 27, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Twelve pp. See Link: "Mit schwarz Grunde und Tapfer Keit": The Military Record of Sgt. Paul Ernst Kaess
 50. See 'The True History of Brian Paul Kaess in Mexico: From 2006 tom 2025' by Brian Paul Kaess on September 22, 2025, at Zenodo.org. 1st of Trilogy. Twenty pp. See Link: The True History of Brian Paul Kaess in Mexico: From 2006 to 2025
 51. See 'Kaess Miscellany: A Chronicle from 2025 Onwards' by Brian Paul Kaess on September 23, 2025, at Zenodo.org. 2nd of Trilogy. Nine pp. See Link: Kaess Miscellany: A Chronicle from 2025 Onwards
 52. See "What It Is, Not What It Ain't! Escalating Tensions in the Mexican Drug War" by Brian Paul Kaess on September 11, 2025, at Zenodo.org. 3rd of Trilogy. Twelve pp. See Link: "What It Is, Not What It Ain't! Escalating Tensions in the Mexican Drug War"
 53. See 'Echoes from the Fenceline' by Brian Paul Kaess on July 7, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Poetry. Single page. See Link: Echoes from the Fenceline Also available in FS Catalog: Echoes from the Fenceline
 54. See 'Fragments' by Brian Paul Kaess on October 26, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Poetry. Single page. See Link: Fragments
 55. See 'The Kaessaron' by Brian Paul Kaess on September 20, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Ten pp. See Link: The Kaessaron

56. See 'Selected Essays of Brian Paul Kaess: Covering the Years from 1976 to 2025, Volumes 1-8, with an Introduction by Brian Paul Kaess' on October 29, 2025, at Zenodo.org. Some of these are slimmer & outdated versions of essays found elsewhere. Thirty-one pp. & twenty-eight pp. & thirty-four pp. & thirty-two pp. & thirty-six pp. & thirty-nine pp., thirty pp., & twenty-six pp., representing each volume. See Link: Selected Essays of Brian Paul Kaess, Volumes 1-8

As the old saying goes, “Publish or perish!”—a phrase Brian likes to amend to “Polish or perish!” much like a stonecutter refining a fine gemstone. An outside observer might say that my work in genealogy enjoyed a fecundity in the past few years, especially 2025. I am happy to say that the above list certainly bears testament to that. Just as the expression “Everything plentiful! Everything dear!” evokes a time of great abundance, and how everything is precious, cherished, and emotionally significant- so, too, these writings hint at an antiquarian sense of family history, trying to 'fill in the gaps' as much as possible and not leave anything lost to time.

Yours,
Brian Paul Kaess
Las Villas, Durango, Mexico